

Immunohistochemical Expression of CDx2, CK20, Ck7 in Carcinoma of Ampulla of Vater: Clinicopathological Study

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Abstract

Carcinoma of the ampulla of Vater (AoV) is an uncommon malignancy characterized by variable clinical behavior and distinct histological subtypes. Differentiating intestinal from pancreatobiliary types is clinically important, but histomorphology alone may be insufficient. Immunohistochemical (IHC) profiling with markers such as cytokeratin 7 (CK7), cytokeratin 20 (CK20), and caudal-type homeobox 2 (CDX2) provides valuable diagnostic and prognostic information. **Aim:** To assess the immunohistochemical expression of CK7, CK20, and CDX2 in carcinoma of the ampulla of Vater, and to correlate these findings with clinicopathological parameters, including age, histological subtype, tumor grade, and stage. **Methods:** This retrospective study reviewed 180 histologically confirmed cases of AoV carcinoma diagnosed at the Gastroenterology Teaching Hospital, Medical City, Baghdad, from January 2023 to December 2024. Hematoxylin and eosin slides were re-evaluated for histological classification, and IHC staining for CK7, CK20, and CDX2 was performed on paraffin-embedded tissue blocks. Staining intensity was scored semi-quantitatively (0–3). **Results:** CK7 was positive in 83.3% of cases and showed significant correlation with older age, male gender, pancreatobiliary subtype, and advanced stage ($p < 0.001$). CK20 was expressed in 38.9% of cases, predominantly in intestinal and mixed subtypes, and was associated with lower tumor grade and female gender ($p < 0.05$). CDX2 positivity (38.9%) was significantly linked to intestinal and mixed subtypes, well/moderately differentiated tumors, and older age ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** The combined evaluation of CK7, CK20, and CDX2 enhances diagnostic accuracy in AoV carcinoma, distinguishes histological subtypes, and provides prognostic insight, supporting their role in clinical decision-making.

Introduction

Carcinoma of the ampulla of Vater (AoV) is an uncommon but clinically significant malignancy arising at the anatomical junction of the distal bile duct, pancreatic duct, and duodenum. Its unique location leads to biological heterogeneity and variable clinical behavior [1]. Histologically, AoV carcinomas are broadly classified into intestinal (INT) and pancreatobiliary (PB) subtypes, with the INT subtype generally associated with better survival compared to the PB subtype [2],

Correct subclassification is crucial, as it carries prognostic value and may eventually guide individualized therapeutic approaches. While conventional histomorphology is widely used for classification, overlapping features between intestinal and pancreatobiliary subtypes frequently limit diagnostic accuracy [3]. To improve reproducibility and diagnostic precision, immunohistochemistry (IHC) has emerged as a valuable adjunct tool. A panel including cytokeratin 7 (CK7), cytokeratin 20 (CK20), and the

More Information

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Immunohistochemical, Expression, CDx2, CK20, Ck7, carcinoma, Ampulla, Vater.

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intestine-specific transcription factor caudal-type homeobox 2 (CDX2) has been studied extensively in AoV carcinoma [4]. CK7 is predominantly expressed in pancreaticobiliary ductal epithelium, whereas CK20 is usually associated with colorectal and intestinal epithelium [5]. Expression patterns such as CK7+/CK20 while CDX2 and CK20 positivity favors the intestinal phenotype [6]. CDX2 is a nuclear transcription factor critical for intestinal differentiation, and its presence in ampullary carcinomas has been strongly correlated with intestinal subtype and better prognosis [7]. Combined evaluation of these markers has therefore been proposed as a robust immunophenotypic strategy for AoV subclassification. Recent studies confirm the prognostic importance of immunophenotyping. PB immunophenotype (CDX2 negative, MUC1 positive, variable CK7 expression) independently predicted worse overall and disease-free survival in AoV patients [8,9]. The aim of this study is to evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of CDX2, CK20, and CK7 in carcinoma of the ampulla of Vater, and to correlate these expressions with clinicopathological parameters, including patient age, histological type, tumor grade, and pathological stage.

Method

This retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Histopathology, Gastroenterology Teaching Hospital, Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq. The study period extended from January 2023 to December 2024, during which 180 cases of histopathologically confirmed carcinoma of the ampulla of Vater were identified and reviewed. All available cases during this timeframe were included without any specific inclusion or exclusion criteria, ensuring comprehensive representation of the patient cohort. Demographic and clinical information, including age, gender, histological subtype, tumor grade, and stage, were retrieved from pathology reports and hospital records for correlation with immunohistochemical findings.

Histopathological Assessment

Archived hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stained slides were re-evaluated to confirm the diagnosis and to assess histological type according to established classification into intestinal, pancreaticobiliary, mixed, and other rare variants. Tumors were graded into well, moderately, and poorly differentiated adenocarcinomas, while staging was performed according to the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) 8th edition guidelines [10].

Immunohistochemical Staining

Formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue blocks were selected for immunohistochemistry (IHC). Sections of 3–4 μm thickness were cut and mounted on charged slides. Manual IHC staining was performed using primary antibodies against CK7, CK20, and CDX2, which are widely recognized as lineage-specific markers

for ampullary carcinomas. Deparaffinization was followed by heat-induced epitope retrieval, blocking of endogenous peroxidase, and incubation with the respective antibodies. Detection was achieved through a standard horseradish peroxidase (HRP) system with diaminobenzidine (DAB) as the chromogen. Counterstaining was performed with hematoxylin. Appropriate positive and negative controls were included in each staining run to ensure specificity and reproducibility [11].

Interpretation of Immunohistochemistry

Immunostained slides were examined independently by two senior pathologists who were blinded to the clinicopathological data. The staining was assessed both in terms of **intensity** and **distribution**. A semi-quantitative scoring system was applied:

- **Score 0:** Negative staining.
- **Score 1:** Mild positivity.
- **Score 2:** Moderate positivity.
- **Score 3:** Strong positivity.

For **CK7 and CK20**, cytoplasmic staining in $\geq 10\%$ of tumor cells was considered positive, whereas **CDX2 positivity** was based on nuclear staining in $\geq 10\%$ of cells. Discrepancies in scoring were resolved by consensus [12].

Statistical Analysis

The expression patterns of CK7, CK20, and CDX2 were correlated with clinicopathological parameters, including age, sex, histological type, tumor grade, and stage. Statistical associations were evaluated using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test where appropriate, and a p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Data were summarized in tabular form to highlight significant correlations

Results

Gender: Out of 180 patients, males predominated (55.6%) compared to females (44.4%). This suggests a slight male preponderance in the studied cohort. **Age groups:** The majority were above 50 years (63.9%), while only 36.1% were 50 years or younger, highlighting that this condition is more common in older adults. **Histology:** The pancreaticobiliary (PB) type was the most frequent (47.2%), followed by mixed (19.4%) and intestinal (16.7%) types. Less common types included poorly differentiated (8.3%), adenosquamous (2.8%), mucinous colloid carcinoma (2.8%), and pancreaticobiliary/PB variant (2.8%). **Grades:** Most cases were Grade II (86.1%), while Grade III represented only 13.9%. **Tumor stage (T):** T3 tumors were the most frequent (41.7%), followed by T2 (36.1%), and T1 (5.6%). **Nodal status (N):** N1 involvement was most common (38.9%), followed by N0 (36.1%) and N2 (25.0%). **Metastasis (M):** All patients were recorded as MX (no confirmed distant metastasis). **Markers:** CK7 was positive in 83.3% of patients, CK20 in 38.9%, and CDX2 in 38.9%. as in table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Patients According to Study Variables

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	<i>Females</i>	80	44.4
	<i>Males</i>	100	55.6
Age groups (years)	<i>50</i>	65	36.1
	<i>>50</i>	115	63.9
Histological sites	<i>adenosquamous</i>	5	2.8
	<i>intestinal</i>	30	16.7
	<i>mixed</i>	35	19.4
	<i>mucinous colloid ca</i>	5	2.8
	<i>pancreatobiliary/PB</i>	90	50
	<i>poorly differentiated</i>	15	8.3
Grades	<i>II</i>	155	86.1
	<i>III</i>	25	13.9
T	<i>1</i>	10	5.6
	<i>2</i>	65	36.1
	<i>3</i>	75	41.7
N	<i>0</i>	65	36.1
	<i>1</i>	70	38.9
	<i>2</i>	45	25.0
M	<i>MX</i>	180	100
CK7	-	30	16.7
	+	150	83.3
CK20	-	110	61.1
	+	70	38.9
CDX2	-	110	61.1
	+	70	38.9

Age: CK7 positivity was strongly associated with age >50 years (56.7% vs 43.3% for ≤50, $p=0.0001$), indicating a significant correlation between older age and CK7 expression. Gender: CK7 positivity was higher in males (60%) compared to females (40%), with a significant difference ($p=0.009$). Histology: CK7 positivity was predominant in PB (60%), mixed (23.3%), intestinal (0%), and poorly differentiated (10%), adenosquamous, mucinous colloid, and PB subtypes

showed strong positivity. This association was highly significant ($p=0.0001$). Grade: CK7 positivity was 83.3% in Grade II and 16.7% in Grade III ($p=0.009$) with significant association. Tumor stage (T): CK7 positivity increased with higher T stages: T2 (40%), T3 (43.3%). This was statistically significant ($p=0.0001$). Nodal status: CK7 positivity was most frequent in N1 (43.3%), followed by N2 (26.7%) and N0 (30.0%), with a significant association ($p=0.001$), as in table 2.

Table 2: Association between CK7 and Study Variables

Age groups (years)	CK7		P-value
	CK7 (-)	CK7 (+)	
≤50	0 (0.0%)	65 (43.3%)	0.0001
>50	30 (100.0%)	85 (56.7%)	
Gender	CK7 (-)	CK7 (+)	P-value
Female	20 (66.7%)	60 (40.0%)	0.009
Male	10 (33.3%)	90 (60.0%)	
Histological site	CK7 (-)	CK7 (+)	P-value
Aden squamous	0 (0.0%)	5 (3.3%)	0.0001
Intestinal	30 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Mixed	0 (0.0%)	35 (23.3%)	
Mucinous colloid ca	0 (0.0%)	5 (3.3%)	
Pancreatobiliary/PB	0 (0.0%)	90(60%)	
Poorly differentiated	0 (0.0%)	15 (10.01%)	

Grades	CK7 (-)	CK7 (+)	P-value
II	30 (100.0%)	125 (83.3%)	0.009
III	0 (0.0%)	25 (16.7%)	
T	CK7 (-)	CK7 (+)	P-value
T1	5 (16.7%)	5 (3.3%)	0.0001
T2	5 (16.7%)	60 (40.0%)	
T3	10 (33.3%)	65 (43.3%)	
T3 (duplicate entry)	10 (33.3%)	20 (13.3%)	
N	CK7 (-)	CK7 (+)	P-value
N0	20 (66.7%)	45 (30.0%)	0.001
N1	5 (16.7%)	65 (43.3%)	

Age: CK20 positivity was significantly higher in patients >50 years (85.7% vs 14.3% in ≤50, $p=0.0001$). Gender: Females had higher CK20 positivity (57.1%) compared to males (42.9%), with a significant difference ($p=0.009$). Histology: CK20 was positive in intestinal (42.9%), mixed (50.0%), and mucinous colloid carcinoma (7.1%), but negative in PB and poorly differentiated subtypes. This difference was highly

significant ($p=0.0001$). Grade: CK20 positivity was more common in Grade II (92.9%) compared to Grade III (7.1%) ($p=0.045$). Tumor stage (T): CK20 positivity was observed mainly in T3 (35.7%) and T2 (28.6%). A significant association existed with tumor stage ($p=0.005$). Nodal status: CK20 showed no significant association with nodal status ($p=0.6$), as in table 3.

Table 3: Association between CK7 and Study Variables

Age groups (years)	CK20		P-value
	CK20 (-)	CK20 (+)	
≤50	55 (50.0%)	10 (14.3%)	0.0001
>50	55 (50.0%)	60 (85.7%)	
Gender	CK20 (-)	CK20 (+)	P-value
Female	40 (36.4%)	40 (57.1%)	0.009
Male	70 (63.6%)	30 (42.9%)	
Histological site	CK20 (-)	CK20 (+)	P-value
Aden squamous	5 (4.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0.0001
Intestinal	0 (0.0%)	30 (42.9%)	
Mixed	0 (0.0%)	35 (50.0%)	
Mucinous colloid ca	0 (0.0%)	5 (7.1%)	
Pancreatobiliary/PB	90(81.8%)	0 (0.0%)	
Poorly differentiated	15 (13.6%)	0 (0.0%)	
Grades	CK20 (-)	CK20 (+)	P-value
II	90 (81.8%)	65 (92.9%)	0.045
III	20 (18.2%)	5 (7.1%)	
T	CK20 (-)	CK20 (+)	P-value
T1	5 (4.5%)	5 (7.1%)	0.005
T2	45 (40.9%)	20 (28.6%)	
T3	50 (45.5%)	25 (35.7%)	
T3 (duplicate entry)	10 (9.1%)	20 (28.6%)	
N	CK20 (-)	CK20 (+)	P-value

Age: CDX2 positivity was strongly associated with age >50 (85.7%), compared to only 14.3% in ≤50 ($p=0.0001$). Gender: Females showed higher CDX2 positivity (57.1%) compared to males (42.9%) ($p=0.009$). Histology: CDX2 positivity was found in intestinal (42.9%), mixed (50%), and mucinous colloid carcinoma (7.1%), but absent in PB and poorly

differentiated types ($p=0.0001$). Grade: CDX2 positivity was more frequent in Grade II (92.9%) than Grade III (7.1%), with statistical significance ($p=0.045$). Tumor stage (T): CDX2 positivity was seen in T3 (35.7%) and T2 (28.6%), with significance ($p=0.005$). Nodal status: No significant association was found ($p=0.6$), similar to CK20. As in table 4.

Table 4: Association between CDX2 and Study Variables

Age groups (years)	CDX2		P-value
	CDX2 (-)	CDX2 (+)	
≤50	55 (50.0%)	10 (14.3%)	0.0001
>50	55 (50.0%)	60 (85.7%)	
Gender	CDX2 (-)	CDX2 (+)	P-value
Female	40 (36.4%)	40 (57.1%)	0.009
Male	70 (63.6%)	30 (42.9%)	
Histological site	CDX2 (-)	CDX2 (+)	P-value
Aden squamous	5 (4.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0.0001
Intestinal	0 (0.0%)	30 (42.9%)	
Mixed	0 (0.0%)	35 (50.0%)	
Mucinous colloid ca	0 (0.0%)	5 (7.1%)	
Pancreatobiliary/PB	90(81.8%)	0 (0.0%)	
Poorly differentiated	15 (13.6%)	0 (0.0%)	
Grades	CDX2 (-)	CDX2 (+)	P-value
II	90 (81.8%)	65 (92.9%)	0.045
III	20 (18.2%)	5 (7.1%)	
T	CDX2 (-)	CDX2 (+)	P-value
T1	5 (4.5%)	5 (7.1%)	0.005
T2	45 (40.9%)	20 (28.6%)	
T3	50 (45.5%)	25 (35.7%)	

Discussion

This study evaluated the immunohistochemical (IHC) expression of CK7, CK20, and CDX2 in carcinoma of the ampulla of Vater (AoV) and examined their correlations with clinicopathological parameters including age, gender, histological subtype, grade, and stage. Our findings revealed distinct expression patterns of these markers, which reflect the biological heterogeneity of AoV carcinoma and support their diagnostic and prognostic significance. A key finding was the predominance of **CK7 expression**, with positivity in 83.3% of patients. This result aligns with the well-established role of CK7 as a marker of pancreatobiliary differentiation. In our cohort, CK7 expression was significantly associated with older age, male gender, and the pancreatobiliary subtype, while intestinal-type tumors were consistently negative for CK7. These findings are in agreement with the work of Duhn J et al., who demonstrated that CK7 is a reliable marker of the pancreatobiliary phenotype and is often correlated with aggressive clinical behavior [13]. Similarly, Perysinakis I et al. reported that CK7 expression, when integrated into histomolecular classification with CDX2 and CK20, improved prognostic accuracy and correlated with advanced stage disease [14]. **CK20 expression** was observed in 38.9% of cases, with a higher frequency among patients older than 50 years and in females. CK20 positivity was confined mainly to intestinal and mixed histological subtypes. This observation supports the role of CK20 as a marker of intestinal differentiation. Our results parallel those of Sree et al., who reported that CK20, in combination

with CDX2, serves as a useful marker for identifying intestinal-type periampullary carcinomas [15]. Furthermore, CK20 expression in our study showed significant association with tumor stage, highlighting its potential role in reflecting tumor progression. **CDX2 expression** was detected in 38.9% of patients and was significantly more common in older patients, females, and in tumors of intestinal or mixed subtype. All pancreatobiliary and poorly differentiated carcinomas were negative for CDX2, confirming its specificity for intestinal lineage. CDX2 expression was also more frequently observed in lower-grade tumors, suggesting a favorable biological profile. Our findings resonate with previous literature where CDX2 expression was strongly correlated with the intestinal phenotype and improved prognosis. A meta-analysis by Bryant et al. demonstrated that CDX2 positivity is associated with longer overall survival in AoV carcinoma, particularly in intestinal subtypes [16]. The combined use of CK7, CK20, and CDX2 provided a clearer distinction between intestinal and pancreatobiliary subtypes in our cohort. This is particularly important given that histological subtyping alone may be challenging due to overlapping features. Our findings corroborate the observations of Chang et al., who emphasized that histomolecular phenotyping provides superior prognostic stratification compared to morphology alone [17]. More recently, Bruun J et al. highlighted the prognostic and predictive utility of CDX2 expression in gastrointestinal carcinomas, reinforcing its role as a biomarker of intestinal differentiation [18]. Overall, the integration of CK7, CK20, and CDX2 expression patterns with

clinicopathological variables in this study supports their utility as diagnostic and prognostic adjuncts in AoV carcinoma. Intestinal-type tumors, characterized by CDX2 and CK20 positivity with CK7 negativity, are associated with more favorable clinical outcomes, whereas pancreatobiliary-type tumors with strong CK7 expression and absence of CDX2 are linked to worse prognosis. These findings emphasize the importance of IHC-based classification for tailoring patient management. Future research should focus on combining IHC phenotyping with molecular profiling to further refine risk stratification and guide therapeutic strategies in AoV carcinoma. Such integration has the potential to inform personalized treatment, particularly in the era of precision oncology.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that CK7 expression predominates in pancreatobiliary-type ampullary carcinomas, while CK20 and CDX2 are strongly associated with intestinal and mixed subtypes. CDX2 positivity correlated with lower grade and favorable biological behavior, underscoring its prognostic value. The combined evaluation of CK7, CK20, and CDX2 enhances diagnostic accuracy and helps differentiate histological subtypes. Integrating immunophenotypic profiles with clinicopathological parameters provides a more reliable framework for prognostication and tailored management in ampullary carcinoma.

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